

DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF AUDITING PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT IN THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of current research in the field of auditing personnel management in an organization and finding ways to solve the problem of improving the personnel audit system in modern enterprises. A personnel management audit is considered as a comprehensive mechanism for assessing and monitoring performance indicators of the entire set of personnel processes of an enterprise that form the personnel management system.

Keywords: personnel management audit, personnel audit, personnel management system, personnel processes, performance indicators of personnel processes.

INTRODUCTION

As a rule, in the world practice of enterprises, personnel management is organized according to a systemic principle. However, as research results show, in Uzbekistan it is customary to use ready-made management models, many of which were developed by specialists from other countries and are not entirely suitable for the economic, social, national and other characteristics of Uzbekistan. Therefore, it can be argued that domestic personnel management systems are still at the stage of their formation. At the formation stage, high-quality and timely comprehensive diagnostics of personnel management systems are especially important. Researchers consider personnel management audit, or personnel audit, to be the most effective tool for such diagnostics [10]. To make certain decisions regarding the management of an organization, it is important that the information on the basis of which conclusions are drawn is timely and reliable. This means that at all levels of business activity it is necessary to collect it and periodically update it, that is, conduct an audit.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Simonin P.V. and Artyukhin D.V. pay attention to the study of the problem associated with personnel and diagnostics, while the personnel of an enterprise is understood as “a set of individuals who are in relations with it as a legal entity, regulated by an employment contract” [1]. During the human resource audit process, it is very important to study issues related to management. Simonin P.V. and Krasnozhenova G.F. interpret management as “the most effective way of purposeful influence of the subject of management on an object in order to change

the initial state and bring it to a higher quality level” [8]. Within the framework of the institutional approach, “ensuring the effective implementation of social and labor relations is not possible without the availability of information on the regulation of wage issues in collective agreements and agreements, as well as internal social factors: work style, team cohesion, professional composition of personnel, communications, rational labor standards and etc.”[8]. Institutions in modern society take the form of legal norms and traditions that have proven their effectiveness for all aspects of labor relations. Therefore, it is important to understand the degree of compliance of the enterprise’s personnel management system with current laws and accepted standards. An analytical tool such as an audit allows you to determine the degree of this compliance. Under the audit of the personnel management system (personnel audit) Tsvetkova E.V. understands “the process of a comprehensive analysis of all elements of the company’s personnel management, the methods of interaction of all participants in this process, the procedure for setting tasks, the procedure for performing work and reporting” [9].

METHODOLOGY

The article uses methods such as analysis of published scientific literature on personnel auditing, audit procedures, data processing and comparison.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The word “audit” itself, which comes from the Latin root “audieus” - “to listen”, implies the verification of mainly paper reports relating to one or another area of the company’s activities. The purpose of the audit is not only to identify possible violations, but also to prevent them, as well as to provide consultations, thanks to which it is possible to increase efficiency in the audited area. Currently, the activities of auditors have expanded significantly, including the area of personnel management. A personnel audit can be called a consulting activity that, through expert analysis, establishes the personnel potential of an organization and its effectiveness. The auditor examines documentation related to the selection, registration, relocation and dismissal of employees of the organization for compliance of the documents with the requirements of legislative acts of Uzbekistan. A personnel audit is not only a way to carry out an audit, that is, a statement of facts, but also a tool for overcoming existing problems, the ultimate goal of which is to increase the profitability of the organization. By determining the degree of correctness of maintaining personnel documentation and studying additional factors reflected in it, the auditor can draw conclusions regarding:

- the effectiveness of the personnel policy adopted in a given organization in relation to its main goal;
- correct application of the legislative framework;
- finding reserves for improving personnel management;

- identifying negative aspects that hinder personnel efficiency, analyzing possible ways to eliminate them.

In what cases should an organization pay attention to studying the personnel situation by conducting a personnel audit? You can carry out this procedure at any time, but it will bring the greatest benefit in situations such as:

- change of leadership in the organization;
- dismissal of the head of the HR department;
- preparation for external audit by control bodies;
- formation of a database of personnel documents for archival storage;
- innovations in the legislative sphere regarding employment and dismissal;
- unexpected sudden changes in personnel, for example, lockout and etc.

Table 1

Stages of personnel audit

Stage 1 – preparation.	It is necessary to clearly establish the purpose of the audit and define the objectives. The main factors of the future research are clarified: who will conduct it, in what time frame, on what sample and with what methods. Management issues an order or instruction.
Stage 2 – data collection.	Information is accumulated by studying documents, observing personnel, conducting surveys, questionnaires, etc. At this stage, the initial processing of the information received occurs.
Stage 3 – interpretation of the information received.	Compilation of data into a form convenient for analysis (lists, tables, graphs, diagrams, etc.), conclusions based on the processing methods used and comparison with previous indicators or data from other organizations.
Stage 4 – final.	Formation of the audit report, results and recommendations.

To study human resources, auditors use:

-analytical methods – study of documentation and statistical performance indicators;

-socio-psychological methods – observation, surveys, questionnaires, conversations;

-economic methods – comparison of financial indicators with social factors.

Based on the results of the analysis of the organization’s personnel activities, conclusions can be drawn regarding:

- staffing of the organization;
- quality of personnel management in the company;
- predominant leadership style;
- internal climate in the team;
- opportunities for introducing innovations;

- needs to improve personnel qualifications;
- potential for building a career at different job levels;
- reasons for identified negative factors and ways to overcome them.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the methods of external assessment of an organization's activities, in particular labor. Analysis of indicators represents a new direction of audit activity - the formation of an audit of the labor sphere. Currently, audit is used only when examining the financial sector of an organization. Checking specific areas of labor activity - labor standards, workplace organization, labor protection, personnel management allows you to control the situation in the labor sphere at a minimum level. We propose to interpret the audit of the personnel management system as a periodically conducted examination in the field of personnel management, which includes a set of measures to collect information, analyze it and evaluate, based on the data obtained, the effectiveness of using the labor potential of the enterprise in accordance with its development strategy, as well as the development of an organizational program changes related to work with personnel. In my opinion, an audit is not a type of examination, but is an independent, comprehensive, formalized method of long-term improvement of an organization's efficiency through improving personnel management systems, increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of labor potential, which in its characteristics reflects the requirements of objective and professional attention to situational conditions. As can be seen from the definitions presented, the concept being studied is complex and multi-component, and is interpreted as an independent method (similar to the examination method), which has such mandatory characteristics as complexity, focus and practical significance. The personnel management audit system performs the task of assessing and controlling personnel processes, the essence of which is "monitoring an object in order to verify compliance with a given state.

One of the main characteristics of the efficiency of using enterprise personnel is labor productivity, which can be increased by using both economic methods and management methods. To increase the effectiveness of management methods used within the enterprise's personnel management system, it is necessary to use an effective personnel management audit system. It is this that will allow us to evaluate the effectiveness of the applied management methods in combination and separately, highlighting problem areas and growth areas. As a result of our research, we can say that the solution to analytical problems of restructuring is ensured by using the analysis method as an analytical apparatus for studying economic processes. Indeed, high-quality and comprehensive analysis, which is only possible with the use of an audit tool, allows us to develop better management decisions. And regular auditing will ensure that these decisions are timely. Thus, the personnel management audit

system in modern enterprises plays an important role in increasing the controllability of individual personnel processes and the characteristics of the use of personnel labor, as well as in improving the quality and speed of management decisions made. However, only an effective audit system can fulfill this role. Let's consider the main recommendations for increasing the efficiency of the personnel management audit system.

We determine that an effective HR audit system is based not on the well-known four stages, but on the more extensive six. To the main four stages (preparation, data collection, analysis, development of recommendations), researchers consider it important to add such stages as “selection of audit specialists” and “monitoring the implementation of corrective measures in the personnel management process.” Accordingly, when forming a personnel audit system at an enterprise, special attention should be paid to the competencies and qualifications of auditors (external or internal). We came to the conclusion that when organizing a personnel management audit system, it is important to accurately select a tool depending on the tasks set by the customer, as well as a comprehensive approach. It is an integrated approach to analyzing the criteria for the effectiveness of personnel management that will most quickly and accurately identify problem areas. Therefore, a compliance audit program aimed at determining the compliance of enterprise processes with legal requirements must be supplemented with a strategic personnel audit program, which is aimed at revealing the reasons for the slowdown in achieving strategic objectives in the field of personnel management of a particular enterprise.

As the analysis showed, in order to improve the audit system personnel management, it is necessary to carry out systematic training of internal auditors, which will consist of developing their analytical abilities, deepening professional knowledge in the field of personnel management, as well as acquiring skills in developing and implementing projects to improve personnel processes at the enterprise. Also, increasing the efficiency of the audit system is facilitated by the use of a comprehensive audit (a program that includes compliance audit and strategic audit criteria) on a regular basis.

REFERENCES

1. Artyukhina D.V., Simonin P.V. Development of a program to increase personnel productivity at the enterprise, 2016. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: https://elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_28435241_16132790.pdf/ (date appeals:01/23/2019).
2. Dolinin A.Yu. Personnel Audit. Ryaz. state University named after S.A. Yesenina. Ryazan, 2011. 56 p.

3. Karpova E.G., Dimova K.B. Analysis of Russian experience in building a personnel management system at service enterprises // Economics and modern management: theory and practice: collection. Art. by mother LIII intl. scientific-practical conf. No. 9 (52). Novosibirsk: SibAK, 2015.
4. Krasnozhenova G.F., Simonin P.V. Human resources management: Textbook. allowance. M.: INFRA-M, 2012. 159 p.
5. Maymina E.V. Principles and methods of restructuring the activities of an organization // National interests: priorities and security. 13/2009. P. 54.
6. Matveev A.V. Personnel Audit tools // Reshetnev Readings. 2016. pp. 481-485. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/instrumenty-kadrovogo-audita/> (date of access: 01/23/2019).
7. Nikonova T.V. Management audit: personnel. M.: Exam, 2002. 223 p.
8. Simonin P.V., Bogacheva T.V., Danilova V.A. Regulation and institutionalization of social and labor relations // Internet journal "Naukovedenie". Volume 7. No. 1, 2015. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://naukovedenie.ru/PDF/97EVN115.pdf>(free access). Cap. from the screen. Language Russian, English DOI: 10.15862/97EVN115/ (date of access: 02/26/2019).
9. Tsvetkova E.V. Personnel audit in the personnel management system // Economics and modern management: theory and practice: collection of articles. Art. by mother X intl. scientific-practical conf. Part II. Novosibirsk: SibAC, 2012. URL: <https://sibac.info/conf/econom/x/26824> (access date: 02/03/2019).
10. Chesnokova A.N. Personnel audit as an effective enterprise management system // Scientific community of students: Interdisciplinary research: collection. Art. according to mat. XXXIII international stud. scientific-practical conf. No. 22 (33). [Electronic resource]. Access mode: [https://sibac.info/archive/meghdis/22\(33\).pdf/](https://sibac.info/archive/meghdis/22(33).pdf/) (access date: 01/23/2019)